

Synthesis of Polycyclic Diterpenes[†]

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I feel greatly honoured for being invited by the Indian Chemical Society to deliver the Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Lecture, 1985. Acharya Ray was the father of Indian Chemistry and laid the foundation for chemical education, research and industry in our country. We owe a deep sense of gratitude to the great Acharya. In this presentation I have chosen to present mainly on some contributions made from the laboratories of Organic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, in the field of the Synthesis of polycyclic diterpenoids during the last three decades.

The known polycyclic diterpenoids¹ having a complement of twenty carbon atoms in their molecular framework were earlier confined to resin acids. A large number of diterpenoids have been and are being characterised having broad range of biological activities including cytotoxic agents, antibiotics, plant hormones, insecticides, cattle poisons and cardiac active compounds, and with wide variations in their structural patterns. The principal skeleton types of the diterpenoids can be classified into more than twenty groups; amongst these there are compounds with unusual stereochemical complexities, and highly rearranged skeleton patterns, for example, taxanes, forskolin and ingenes, which have attracted current intensification of synthetic interest.

Ring-C-aromatic diterpene resin acids :

Since full structure determinations of a number of long known diterpenes, abietic acid (1), pimaric acid (2), dehydroabietic acid (3) and podocarpic acid (4) had been completed¹ in the previous decade, the synthesis of diterpene resin acids and the related hydrophenanthrenes was an attractive area of research when the author joined the laboratory of the Association as a Ph D. student with Professor P. C. Dutta in the early spring of 1954. Incidentally, the next few years witnessed the most exciting period of synthetic achievements in this field^a.

Some of the major developmenets in the area of the synthetic chemistry in resin acids are briefly discussed here. In 1932 several groups^{1b} including Bardhan and Sengupta^a in the University College of Science, Calcutta, reported novel syntheses of retene (5) and pimanthrene (6), two key degradation products of abietic acid (1) and pimaric acid (2), respectively, thereby providing their skeleton structures. The new and general synthetic methods

for phenanthrene developed in course of that work not only accomplished the objectives in view but paved the way to the subsequent syntheses of compounds related to natural products other than resin acids. The acid-catalysed intramolecular

cyclialkylation reaction developed by Haworth and his coworkers⁴ constitutes one of the simplest and most widely used methods for the synthesis of ring-C-aromatic resin acids and various other diterpenoids. In 1939 Haworth and Barker^{4a} first reported the cyclisation of β -phenylethylcyclohexene derivatives 9, 10 and 11, derived from the respective cyclohexanones 7 and 8 with a sulphuric acid and acetic acid mixture and obtained directly the corresponding tricycyclic acids 13, 14 and 15, respectively, in very poor yields, as a single diastereoisomer in each case (Scheme 1). The stereochemistries of these acids are represented as assigned by

Scheme 1

the later workers. For example, the identifications of the acids 13, 14 and 15 were provided by our own works to be described. Particular mention should be made here that the isolation⁵ of callistrisic acid

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(15) from natural sources in 1967 is of historic interest, as this renders the Haworth synthesis^{4a} as the first total synthesis of a naturally occurring diterpenoid in racemic form, even before it was known. In 1956 King *et al.*⁶ identified the major product from the polyphosphoric acid (PPA) cyclisation of the carbinol (17) (Scheme 2) as (\pm)-ethyl *O*-methylpodocarpate (18) and correlated this with the corresponding acid (16), prepared independently by Bhattacharyya⁷ and Haworth *et al.*^{4b} through the unsaturated ester (12) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 2

Parham *et al.*⁸ in 1955 reported the conversion of the keto-lactone (19) with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-HCl}$ to a keto-acid (20) (Scheme 3) as assigned later from our investigation. One of the two acids obtained by the reduction of the carbonyl group was proved to be the *cis*-acid (21).

Scheme 3

The highly stereocontrolled synthesis of (\pm)-dehydroabiatic acid (3) by Stork and Schulenberg⁹ in 1956 was indeed a milestone in diterpene chemistry. The synthesis proceeded according to the sequence 22 \rightarrow 24 (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

After methylation of the β -tetralone (22; R=H) by enamine method to the ketone (22; R=Me), a ring-annulation using ethyl vinyl ketone gave the tricyclic ketone (23), in which the angular methyl group forced the subsequent alkylation with bromoacetic ester to occur from the less hindered rear face of the molecule. Catalytic hydrogenation of the ester (24) so obtained, also occurred from the rear and removal of the carbonyl groups and a Barbier-Wieland degradation of the side chain finally provided (\pm)-dehydroabiatic acid (3).

Considerable emphasis was given to this area in our laboratory, particularly towards the synthesis of diterpenoid resin acids. As a prelude to the long involvement in these synthetic investigations, a synthesis of a tribasic acid (25), structurally identical with the C_{12} -acid, an important oxidation product of abiatic acid (1), was successfully completed in 1953 by Rao and Bagchi¹⁰. It should be mentioned here that the synthesis of another key degradation product of 1, the C_{11} -acid (26) was achieved by Banerjee *et al.*¹¹ in 1966.

The first phase of our investigations directed at the stereocontrolled total syntheses of diterpene resin acids stems from the development of suitable methods for generating *gem*-carboxyl methyl functionality from the carbonyl group with such stereochemical control that a tricyclic ketone (27), reported by Stork and Burgstahler¹², and from our laboratory by Saha *et al.*¹³ would lead to two diastereoisomeric acids at C-4 with respect to the C-10 angular methyl group, having stereochemistry related to dehydroabiatic acid (3) and podocarpic acid (4). In this direction two methods were successfully worked out^{14,15} with cyclohexanone (28) (Scheme 5) through the unsaturated cyanoester (29) leading to the desired acid (30). When applied

Scheme 5

to the decalone (31), synthesised first in our laboratory¹⁵, one of the methods (route A) gave the acid (33) (Scheme 6) through the unsaturated cyanoester (32)^{15,16}, the complete stereochemistry of which was confirmed from the later studies from this¹⁷ and other¹⁸ laboratories. The second method

Scheme 6

(route B), however, followed an unexpected course of reduction of the double bond¹⁸ in **32** as well as in the unsaturated cyano-ester (**34**)¹⁹ from the tricyclic ketone (**27**).

After completion of the aforementioned model studies the tricyclic ketone (**27**), which appeared to exist mainly in the *cis*-form (and as confirmed subsequently), was subjected to the sequence of reactions (**27**→**37**) (Scheme 7) resulting in the first *stereocontrolled* total synthesis of (\pm)-5-*epi*-desisopropyldehydroabietic acid (**38**)¹⁹. A condensation of **27** with ethyl cyanoacetate gave the unsaturated

Scheme 7

esters (**34**) to which hydrocyanic acid was added stereospecifically from the unhindered backface of the molecule to give the adduct **35**, from which the acid **36** was obtained. Bromination of the silver salt of this acid gave a bromomethyl compound (**37**), which when reduced and saponified gave the acid (**38**). Despite the conceptual simplicity, the stereochemical assignments shown in the above sequence demanded independent confirmation. The method used for **27** was later extended²⁰ with the isopropyl ketone (**39**) through the sequence (**39**→**43**) (Scheme 7), resulting in the first total synthesis of (\pm)-5-*epi*dehydroabietic acid (**44**).

However, besides the aforementioned acid (**38**), m.p. 146–47°, where at least the relative stereochemistry of the C-4 and C-10 centres was assured from the mode of its synthesis there was practically no stereochemical information for the remaining three racemates melting at 232–33° (Haworth and Barker^{4a}), and 205–07° and 186–87° (Parham *et al.*⁸) existed in the literature of that time. It, therefore, became of importance to settle²¹ the stereochemical assignments of these acids. It was attractive first to develop a simple synthetic method for the two possible deoxypodocarpic acid epimers (**14** and **21**) and their interconversions and correlation with podocarpic acid (**4**). The desired objective was realised²¹ in an extremely simple manner (Scheme 8). Thus, conjugate addition of hydrogen cyanide to the unsaturated ketone (**46**), prepared from Hagemann's ester (**45**), followed by hydrolysis and esterification gave the keto-ester (**47**) in a high overall yield. Reaction with methylmagnesium iodide and treatment with oxalic acid in boiling toluene then gave a mixture of the unsaturated ester (**49**) and the lactone (**48**), which on cyclisation with PPA gave a separable mixture of the two epimers, **14** (m.p. 232–33°) and **21** (m.p. 205–07°) identical with the samples prepared by Haworth and Barker^{4a} and Parham *et al.*⁸. The above sequence (**50**→**52**+**53**) (Scheme 8) was also successfully extended²⁰ for the synthesis of (\pm)-callitricic acid (**15**) (identical with the sample prepared by Haworth and Barker^{4a}) and (\pm)-5-*epi*callitricic acid (**54**).

The (\pm)-deoxypodocarpic acid (**14**)²² was converted to (\pm)-podocarpic acid (**4**) by a Friedel-Crafts acetylation of the methyl ester (**55**), giving the ketone (**56**), followed by perbenzoic acid oxidation and hydrolysis of the resulting acetate (Scheme 9). The *cis*-acid (**21**) was also synthesised²² by a stereocontrolled route through alkylation of the *t*-amyl ester (**58**) of the acid (**57**), prepared from the ketone (**27**). This was converted to the *trans*-ester (**55**) through oxidation²³ of the respective ester (**59**) to the diketone (**60**) and catalytic hydrogenolysis of the resulting enol-acetate (Scheme 9).

Scheme 8

Scheme 9

It was clearly evident that the remaining isomer, i.e. (\pm)-desisopropyl dehydroabiatic acid (64) remained to be described. It was unlikely that the acid melting at 186–87°, derived along with the acid (21), by Parham *et al.*⁸, from the keto-acid (20), could be assigned this stereochemistry because of the improbability of epimerisation at C-4. The possibility of that acid being an eutectic mixture of the acids 14 and 21 appeared more likely. Finally, the desired acid (64), m.p 174–75°, was synthesised²² from 1-methyl-2-tetralone (61) by a sequence (61→64) (Scheme 10) analogous to the previously described synthesis of dehydroabiatic acid (*loc. cit.*).

Scheme 10

Thus, syntheses and stereochemical assignments of all the racemates represented by structures 14, 21, 64 and 38, namely, the *trans*- and *cis*-deoxypodocarpic acids and *trans*- and *cis*-desisopropyldehydroabiatic acids were achieved from our laboratories by 1960²². At about the same time all the four acids were prepared^{23,24} in optically active forms from podocarpic acid (4) and dehydroabiatic acid (3) and its nitrile. Two other interesting methods were developed later by Dutta and

Dasgupta, and their coworkers^{17b,25} in our laboratories for the synthesis of the racemic acids 38, 64 and 14.

An interesting result which emerged out of the aforementioned investigations indicated that acid-catalysed intramolecular cyclalkylation reactions give only *trans*- and *cis*-podocarpic acid type products. Consistent mechanism for these stereochemical results have been advanced by our groups²⁶, and based on such a concept a highly improved stereoselective total synthesis (41% overall yield as compared to *ca* 0.4% yield by Bhattacharyya⁷ and Haworth and Moore^{4b}) of (\pm)-*O*-methylpodocarpic acid (16) has been realised²⁷ in our laboratory (Scheme 11). This involves Haworth cyclisation⁴ of a 9:1 mixture of the diastereoisomeric lactones 66 and 67, prepared through the easily accessible keto-ester (65) by reaction with MeMgI followed by treatment with toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid in boiling benzene.

Investigations in the basic ring systems of the resin acids were further pursued leading to simple and general stereocontrolled syntheses^{28,29} of all the four racemates of ring-C-aromatic-20-nor-diterpene resin acids (13, 70–72; R=H), starting from the ketoester (47; R=H) (Scheme 12) used for the synthesis of podocarpic acid (*loc. cit.*). The acid (13; R=H) was found to be identical with the sample prepared according to Haworth and Barker^{4a} through cyclialkylation route^{26a}. Following the general method the corresponding 13-methoxy derivatives were also synthesised³⁰. More recently, Kametani *et al.*³¹ have reported nonstereo-

Scheme 11

Scheme 12

controlled syntheses of all the four isomers (13, 70–72; R=OMe) and established their stereostructures by direct comparisons with our samples. In addition to the importance of the 20-nor-acids for the chemical and conformational studies³⁹ some of these have been used as the key intermediates in the syntheses of diterpene alkaloids, to be described. Important mechanistic information concerning the effects of a neighbouring carboxyl group in the chemical and catalytic reduction of a styrenoid bond^{32,38} or a benzylic lactone moiety³⁴ gathered in those studies have been gainfully employed in the stereocontrolled generation of several chiral centres in a single-step process.

Synthesis of ring-C-aromatic tricyclic diterpenes :

Parallel to the synthetic studies on resin acids, work was begun in our laboratories on the synthesis ring-C-aromatic tricyclic diterpenes having a podocarpatriene skeleton. In this context it should

be noted that the first synthesis of (±)-ferruginol (76) was achieved by King *et al.*³⁵ through non-stereoselective ring closure of the alcohol (73), obtained in two stages from *p*-methoxyphenylacetylene and 2,2,6-trimethylcyclohexanone, to a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of 12-methoxy-podocarpatrienes (74 and 75), from which (76) was obtained (Scheme 13).

Later Raman and Rao³⁶ reported a synthesis of 75, and hence (±)-ferruginol (76) using the β-tetralone approach similar to that used by Strok *et al.* for the synthesis of (±)-dehydroabietic acid (*loc. cit.*). The synthesis of (±)-nimbiol methyl ether (79a; R=OMe) by Ramchandran and Dutta³⁷ in 1960 followed a parallel course (Scheme 14). Thus, the appropriately substituted β-tetralone (77) was annulated to the tricyclic ketone (78) which was methylated and reduced to 79. On oxidation by chromic acid the tricyclic ether (79) gave (±)-nimbiol methyl ether (79a; R=OMe).

Scheme 13

Scheme 14

A stereocontrolled synthesis of (\pm)-semperviol acetate (**56c**) was achieved by us^{9a} through (\pm)-methyl 12-acetyldeoxypodocarpate (**56**), an intermediate used in our total synthesis of (\pm)-podocarpic acid (**4**), involving a sequence (**56**→**56c**) (Scheme 15). On condensation with methymagnesium iodide the ketone (**56**) gave the respective carbinol which on hydrogenolysis afforded the 12-isopropyl derivative (**56a**). The ester (**56a**) was transformed to the *gem*-dimethyl intermediate (**56b**). The synthesis of **56c** was completed by a Friedel-Crafts acetylation and oxidation of the resulting methyl ketone with perbenzoic acid.

Two typical example of the conversions of the known 2-phenylethylcyclohexenones **46** and **80**, prepared from Hagemann's ester (**45**), into the respective *gem*-dimethylcyclohexanones **81** and **82**, and their transformations into the previously reported podocarpatrienes **87** and **88** are shown in Scheme 16.

The crude alcohols **83** and **84** on cyclisation with $\text{MeSO}_3\text{H}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ at room temperature according to the method of Axon *et al.*⁴¹ afforded the respective *trans*-cyclised products **87** and **88** in excellent yield in over 95% purity. Finally the ther (**88**) has been transformed into (\pm)-ferruginol (**76**). Through

Scheme 15

Unlike the ready conjugate addition of cyanide ion to α -substituted- β -methylcyclohexanones, e.g. (**46**→**47**), which has been extensively used by us in the synthesis of the resin acids (*loc cit*), the attempted 1,4-addition of a methyl group to such enones by the usual copper catalysed Grignard reagents or standard cuprate reagents were found unsatisfactory. Very recently^{9a} we have developed a convenient preparation of 2-substituted-3,3-dimethylcyclohexanones, e.g. **81** and **82**, from the corresponding readily accessible cyclohexanones **46** and **80** by using boron trifluoride-ether promoted conjugate addition⁴⁰ of a methyl group with lithium dimethylcuprate, which appears to offer considerable promise as a highly effective general synthetic procedure for a group of naturally occurring tricycyclic ring-C-aromatic diterpenoids having a C-4-*gem*-dimethyl group.

the introduction of the C-13 methyl group in the phenol (**89**), stereocontrolled synthesis⁴² of (\pm)-nimbiol has been achieved.

Interestingly, the cyclohexanols (**92** and **93**), prepared through the respective dimethylcyclohexanones (**90** and **91**), having increased nucleophilicity of the aromatic-ring, on cyclisation with $\text{MeSO}_3\text{H}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ led to a mixtures of the respective *trans*- and the *cis*-products in *ca* 55 : 45 ratio, which were finally converted⁴³ to (\pm)-sugiol methyl ether (**94**), (\pm)-xanthopherol methyl ether (**95**), (\pm)-nimbiol methyl ether (**79a**; R=Me) and (\pm)-5-epioxonimbiol methyl ether (**96**).

This simple and high yield general and convergent sequence certainly constitutes one of the shortest methods so far reported for the synthesis

Scheme 16

of the natural podocarpatriene diterpenoids. The extension of this methodology towards the total synthesis of a few highly oxygenated antitumor diterpenoids is being explored.

Mukherjee and his coworkers⁴⁴, in our laboratories, have developed a synthetic route to podocarpatriene diterpenoids by using reductive methylation as the crucial step. Significant contributions have been made in the synthesis of natural diterpenoids of this group by Nasipuri and his coworkers⁴⁵ at I.I.T., Kharagpur and University of Calcutta.

Plant growth regulating hormones, gibberellins and diterpene alkaloids :

The plant hormones, gibberellins, a group of rearranged polycyclic diterpenoids, were first isolated in 1938. The complete stereostructure of an important member of this group, gibberellic acid (GA_3) (97) was established in the early sixties. A number of C_{20} -gibberellins were also characterised later. A few representative members of the family, for example, GA_{13} (98), GA_{15} (99) and GA_{35} (100), illustrate the various oxidation stages of the C-20 methyl group.

The gibberellins posed a challenging synthetic problem from structural as well as stereochemical points. Some of the reactions generated in our first

generation synthetic designs in resin acids were tested and modified leading to a number of model compounds related to the C_{19} - and C_{20} -gibberellins. Thus, simple stereoselective syntheses^{46,47} of the hydrofluorene lactone (102) and all the four racemates of *gem*-carboxyl-methylhexahydrofluorene derivatives (103–106; $\text{R}^1 = \text{R}^2 = \text{H}$) were developed through the easily accessible unsaturated acid (101; $\text{R} = \text{H}$). Syntheses of the epimeric acids^{48,49} (104–106; $\text{R}^1 = \text{OMe}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$ and $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OMe}$) incorporating aromatic methoxy substituent were also realised. Stereocontrolled total syntheses of the racemic hydrofluorene synthons (107; $\text{R} = \text{H}$ and OMe)^{49,50} and 9-oxo derivative (108)⁵¹ were developed in our laboratory by cyclisation methods.

A general synthetic scheme, that holds considerable potential, was developed by us⁵²⁻⁵⁴ for tetracyclic gibbane and a few phyllocladane synthons. This new and simple synthetic plan is based upon the following reactions (Scheme 17) (i) the intramolecular copper-catalysed carbenoid addition to double bond by thermal-photochemical decomposition of diazoketones (109) followed by a regioselective acid-induced or a regiospecific reductive cleavage of the aromatic conjugated cyclopropyl bond in the pentacyclic ketones (110) to the respective tetracyclic ketones 111 and 112, respectively, (ii) the acid-catalysed intramolecular alkylation of the diazoketones (109) leading to $\Delta^{9,11}$ -tetracyclic ketones (111). Hydrogenolysis of the cyclopropyl ketones (110) in the presence of Pd–C (10%) in ethanol produced the respective 9 α -gibbane (112; $n=1$) or the phyllocladane (112; $n=2$), practically as the

Scheme 17

sole products with regiospecificity and high stereoselectivity, whereas reduction of the styrenoid bond in the gibbenes (**111**; $n=1$) gave a mixture of the corresponding C_9 -epimeric ketones (**112**; $n=1$ and **113**). It was also demonstrated that a small change in substitution pattern in the $\Delta^{9(11)}$ -gibbene can cause drastic change in the stereochemistry of the hydrogenation products. The efficacy of this general method has been demonstrated in the total syntheses⁵⁹ of (\pm)-gibberone (**119a**) and (\pm)-4-methyl-6 β ,13 α -16-oxogibba-1,3,5-(10)-triene (**119b**), two important degradation products of C_{19} - and C_{20} -gibberellins, respectively and a few C -9-epimeric gibbane synthons (**119c-e**) from the corresponding diazomethyl ketones (**117** and **118**). The key intermediate acids (**115** and **116**), for the respective diazoketones, were prepared by cycloaddition reactions through the diene (**114**), obtained from 4-methylindanone.

This strategy of the synthesis of bicyclo[3.2.1]octanone through oxocarbonyl addition reaction has been extended to several other synthesis of the intermediates **120a**⁶⁰ and **120b**⁶¹ towards *B*-seco-gibberellins and *B*-homophyllocladane, respectively. The intramolecular alkylation reactions of γ,δ -unsaturated diazomethyl ketones has been further improved⁶² in our laboratories for preparation of a number of tetracyclic intermediates for diterpenoids⁶³.

Since the synthesis of the C_{20} -gibberellins, e.g. GA_{15} (**99**) and GA_{28} (**100**) posed a crucial problem in the introduction of the C-4 and C-10 (diterpene numberings) functionalised carbon residues in the polycyclic systems, which were analogous to the complex diterpenoid alkaloids atisine (**121**) and veatchine (**122**), we decided to include these in the

targets along with the biogenetically related C_{20} -gibberellins in our third generation synthesis, initiated in the early seventies. Moreover, a great deal of attention was paid during that period on the

synthesis of those complex diterpenoid alkaloids. A tetracyclic synthon (**123**; $\text{R}^1 = \text{OMe}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$) containing ring A, B and C followed by elaboration of the bridged-ring systems D through aromatic moiety was utilised by Nagata *et al.*⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶ in their elegant total syntheses of (\pm)-atisine (**121**)⁶⁴, (\pm)-veatchine (**122**)⁶⁵ and (\pm)-gibberellin A_{15} (**100**)⁶⁶. We developed⁶⁷ a simple stereocontrolled synthesis of the racemic tetracyclic amines (**123**; $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$ or OMe ; $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$) in 1972 through the racemic 20-nor-resin acids (**13**; $\text{R} = \text{H}$ and OMe), simple stereospecific syntheses of which were realised in our earlier works on resin acids (*loc. cit.*). The synthetic approach contains a novel method of angular alkylation at a classically nonreactive centre based upon a regioselective intramolecular α -oxo-carbenoid insertion across the benzylic C-H (at C-10)

bond in the copper-catalysed carbenoid decomposition of the easily accessible α -diazomethyl ketones (124) to the bridged tetracyclic ketones (125). The ketones were converted, in high yields, to the respective dicarboxylic acids (126) which were finally transformed to the tetracyclic amines (123) via the acetates (127), through an efficient route as illustrated in Scheme 18. This sequence represents

Scheme 18

a highly efficient formal total synthesis^{67,68} of racemic GA₁₅, atisine and veatchine. More recently⁶⁴, we have introduced a more effective method of C-H insertion in the diazoketones (124) to the bridged ketones (125) by using a light-induced Ni(acac)₂ catalysed reaction in the place of copper(II) sulphate⁶⁷ or copper(I) oxide^{68,69} as used earlier.

The intramolecular C-H insertion reaction was also extended⁷⁰ for the total synthesis of (\pm)-19 α , 20 α -(acetylamino)-12-hydroxy-5 β ,10 α -podocarpa-8, 11,13-triene, the *N*-acetate of 123 (R¹=H; R²=OH), a major degradation product of atisine and an important synthon towards ajaconine and atidine.

In spite of the successful functionalisation in the hydrophenanthrene diazomethyl ketones, e.g. 124,

an attempted oxocarbenoid insertion reaction of the α -diazomethyl ketone, prepared from the hydrofluorene acid (103), failed to give any characterisable product. We started, therefore, to give adequate consideration to the prospect of developing an alternative and more controlled intramolecular alkylation route based within the broad and intricate carbocyclic frameworks of the readily available starting unsaturated acids, for example, 68 and 101 referred earlier. Towards this goal a remarkably simple and highly efficient synthetic route to the angularly fused cyclobutanones (129) by acid-catalysed intramolecular C-alkylation reactions in the β,γ -unsaturated diazomethyl ketones (128), derivative from the respective unsaturated acid (68), was discovered in our laboratories in 1974⁷¹. The readily available styrenoid cyclobutanones (129) have been further transformed (Scheme 19) to the aforementioned key tetracyclic

Scheme 19

ketones (125) by a remarkable stereospecific rearrangement⁷² of the respective stereoselectively hydrogenated cyclobutanones (130). The rearrangement studies⁷³ of the specifically labelled ketone [³H₂] (130) proved that the process is intramolecular and proceeds through a mechanism as depicted in Scheme 20 leading to [³H₂] (125).

Scheme 20

The β,γ -unsaturated α -diazomethyl ketones (**131**), prepared from the tetrahydrofluorene acids (**101**), also smoothly produced⁷⁸ the respective styrenoid cyclobutanones (**132**) which were transformed through a similar sequence of reactions as used for the hydrophenanthrene derivatives, to the *trans*-hydrofluorene intermediates (**135**) incorporating the C₄- and C₁₀-carboxylic acid groups of GA₁₀₀ (Scheme 21).

Scheme 21

Two other epimeric hydrofluorene acids of **135** were prepared⁷⁴ by a direct regio- and stereo-specific carboxylation of the unsaturated acids (**101**) followed by reduction of the styrenoid bond.

The intramolecular alkylation of diazomethyl ketones directed towards the synthesis of complex diterpenoids, not only provided a facile synthetic entry to a variety of complex polycyclic intermediates⁷⁵ but a few unusual rearrangements were also discovered⁷⁶⁻⁷⁹ during those studies.

Aphidicolin, stemodin and stemarin :

The antiviral tumor-inhibiting fungal metabolite aphidicolin (**136**), discovered in 1973, and its C-9

and C-12 isomeric stemodane derivatives (**137a-d**) are members of a class of diterpenes having an unusual tetracyclic framework. Stemarin (**138**) represents another interesting C/D-ring variant of diterpenes. These compounds have been the subject of much recent synthetic efforts. In conjunction with our synthetic interests in complex

bioactive diterpenes using intramolecular alkylation reactions, we initiated a biogenetic-type synthetic approach (Scheme 22) for the construction of the C/D-ring systems of the aforementioned diterpenes through easily accessible intermediate (**139**; n=2). The successful realisation of a part of our objective, leading to a remarkably simple and potentially useful method of intramolecular α -tert-alkylation resulted in the synthesis of the tetracyclic bicyclo-[2.2.2]octanones (**140**; n=1 and 2) in 1978⁸⁰. Subsequently, we also achieved⁸¹ the transformation of **140** (n=2) to the key tetracyclic intermediates **141** and **142** incorporating the B/C/D-ring carbocyclic systems with an aromatised ring-A related to stemodin and stemarin diterpenes.

Scheme 22

The efficacy of the new acid-catalysed intramolecular C-alkylation and rearrangement reactions developed pertaining to the syntheses of these compounds has been further demonstrated in the synthesis of 140 ($n=1$)⁸¹ and other systems⁸². An unexpected turn taken in the course of these studies led to the discovery of a fascinating intramolecular bond formation reaction with γ,δ - and β,γ -unsaturated methyl ketones with methyl- or ethyl-orthoformates⁸³ in the presence of acid leading to a general method of bridged bicyclo[3.3.1]nonane⁸⁴ and cyclopentenone annulations⁸⁵.

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